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presents

Safe and Sustainable by Design Framework for Circular, Sustainable and Biobased Coatings

PROCEEDINGS

How EU-funded research and innovation projects are contributing to the application of the SSbD to circular, sustainable and biobased coatings

About us

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**Circular
Bio-based
Europe**
Joint Undertaking

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Introduction

Introduction

The European Union's sustainability agenda, driven by the Green Deal, the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS), and the Circular Economy Action Plan, promotes a systemic transition toward safe, renewable, and circular bio-based materials and processes. The CSS aims to reduce chemical-related impacts on health and the environment by progressively phasing out hazardous substances, strengthening traceability, and enhancing management across product life cycles. To turn these ambitions into practice, the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC) is developing a harmonised Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework for chemicals and materials. In the past few years, the European Commission has funded many calls for proposals requesting high-level consortia to work on the assessment based on the SSbD framework, and on the development of recommendations that can further advance the application of the SSbD framework, indicating thresholds that can support the criteria definition and improvements for the assessment of SSbD methodologies, including any specificities related to biobased surfactants. In this webinar, held on **18 November 2025**, European Bioplastics brought together four of these outstanding projects to explore how the Safe and Sustainable by Design framework is being applied to the development of circular, sustainable, and biobased coatings.

The main goals of the webinar were to:

- Exchange practical insights and experiences on implementing SSbD principles in the design and development of circular, sustainable, and biobased coatings, while showcasing the outputs of EU projects.
- Facilitate dialogue across the SSbD innovation landscape.

The webinar also aimed to generate interest in the establishment of a formal Cluster of projects and initiatives working on circular, sustainable, and biobased coatings. The cluster was established in November 2025 and is facilitated by European Bioplastics.

Up next is a series of technical clustering events to consolidate knowledge on sustainable, circular, and biobased coatings.

Stay tuned!

Table of contents

Table of contents

A Cluster for Circular, Sustainable, and Biobased Coatings	6
Implementation of the Safe and Sustainable by Design concept for industrial impact	11
Safe- and sustainable-by-design framework applied to organic and hybrid coatings in the BIO-SUSHY project	14
SSbD and the digital product passport	17
Fluorine-free coatings for textile, kitchenware and packaging applications	21
Conclusions	23
References	26
Contributing Projects	28

About the Cluster

A Cluster for Circular, Sustainable, and Biobased Coatings

European Bioplastics: Chiara Bearzotti and Estela López-Hermoso

This Cluster of projects focusing on Circular, Sustainable, and Biobased Coatings was set up in November 2025 by European Bioplastics, the Cluster facilitator, together with the coordinators of the projects BIO4COAT, led by Funditec, BLUECOAT and SUPREME, both led by the University of Birmingham.

Facilitating a technical exchange among expert researchers will ensure that the voices of the clustered projects are stronger together when presenting project results and policy recommendations in the form of policy briefings to policymakers.

The focus of the Cluster is to allow a technical collaboration across projects. Technical Clustering means liaising with existing projects working on coatings to establish regular formats for exchanging progress, sharing our consolidated knowledge, and setting up joint activities with the sister project. The final activity will be the organisation of a joint policy briefing to share results with policymakers.

In the future, the Cluster will grow with the addition of additional projects and initiatives working on this topic. Any initiative or project can join the Cluster at any time.

European Bioplastics will facilitate the following activities within the Cluster:

- Joint technical discussions (online and/or in person).
- Joint webinars, at least 10, until May 2029, with experts from the clustered projects.
- Two Technical Workshops (longer format): one in-person and one online = Joint networking events with other EU-funded projects to exchange technical knowledge.
- Periodic joint meetings between the clustered projects to exchange information, advice, and updates, at least once per year (online).
- Joint scientific publication and invitation of the clustered projects' representatives to others' annual meetings to share updates.

Based on the knowledge shared in previous activities, a joint policy briefing coordinated by the European Bioplastics will provide a synthesis of outcomes and recommendations from individual projects and initiatives. Joint contributions to policy initiatives, such as replies to Commission consultations or contributions to white papers, are also planned.

If your organisation or project is interested in joining forces with the Cluster and taking the thematic lead of some of the activities, the MoU can be consulted on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/17637735>

Cluster Facilitator at European Bioplastics

Chiara Bearzotti and Estela López-Hermoso

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Presentation

<https://zenodo.org/records/17649039>

Recording

YouTube:

Part 1 <https://youtu.be/pEcDa8qlurU>

Part 2: <https://youtu.be/CVzHcL7xfB0>

About the Speakers

Chiara Bearzotti and Estela López-Hermoso are project managers for the EU-funded projects in European Bioplastics' portfolio. Their passion is to connect players alongside the bioplastics value chain to valorise knowledge.

European Bioplastics

European Bioplastics today represents the interests of more than 80 member companies throughout the European Union. With members from the entire bioplastics value chain, including agricultural feedstock, chemical and plastics industries, as well as industrial users and recycling companies that are located all over the globe and engage in the European market, European Bioplastics serves as a business network as well as an information platform.

Talk 1

Implementation of the Safe and Sustainable by Design concept for industrial impact

IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute:
Emma Strömberg

The transition to Safe- and Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) chemicals, materials and processes is of high priority within Europe. Through the European Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability, the EU recognises that boosting the investment and innovation capacity of SSbD chemicals, materials, and products is key to achieving the EU Green Deal and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals.

During 2022, a framework for the definition of criteria and evaluation procedure for chemicals and materials was published by the EC Joint Research Center (JRC) followed by an EC recommendation promoting this framework. The next steps included operationalisation of SSbD principles and testing of the framework. The framework is under revision, and the revised version will be published by the end of 2025.

The EU-funded project, IRISS, focused on connecting, synergising and transforming the SSbD community in Europe and globally towards a life-cycle thinking that holistically integrates safety, climate neutrality, circularity and the functionality of materials, products and processes throughout their lifecycles. One of the key goals of the project was to create an expanded international SSbD community that provides opportunities for collaboration and knowledge exchange among diverse stakeholders, with a focus on implementing SSbD principles. The project contributed by identifying knowledge and skills gaps for the uptake of the SSbD concept in industrial applications and by conducting a gap analysis of SSbD implementation across several value chains. The invaluable insights from experience and ongoing work in academia and industry, along with the need for further development, contributed to the SSbD Roadmap. The project has resulted in a large SSbD community that will continue to facilitate the transition to safer and sustainable chemicals, processes, materials, and products.

The presentation addresses the identified gaps required for the full implementation of SSbD across various value chains. It also highlights the need for support in operationalising SSbD principles regarding research needs, skills and education development, as well as governance needs.

Recording

YouTube: <https://youtu.be/pEcDa8qIurU>

Project web page: <https://iriss-ssbd.eu/>

About the Speaker

Dr Emma Strömberg is an Associate Professor in polymeric materials, working as a senior researcher at IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute. The work is focused on solutions for waste management, design for recycling, circular economy, chemicals in products and waste, standardisation and design for safe and sustainable materials. Before joining IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute, Emma worked as a researcher at KTH Royal Institute of Technology in Stockholm. Her primary research focused on the environmental interactions of polymeric materials, characterisation of the material properties of conventional polymers and recyclates, biobased materials and composites, and the prevention of biofouling on polymeric surfaces. Emma is currently involved in EU-funded projects on the development of novel sustainable materials (TORNADO, DESIDERATA, INSOIL), chemical risk assessment (PARC) and has coordinated an EU-funded project IRISS - The International ecosystem for accelerating the transition to Safe-and-Sustainable-by-design materials, products and processes. The IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute is an independent non-profit organisation that combines applied research with consultancy services in the fields of the environment and sustainability (climate and energy, sustainable production, water, air quality, circular economy, among other areas).

Talk 2

Safe- and sustainable-by-design organic and hybrid coatings in the BIO-SUSHY project

ITENE: Pau Camilleri Lledó

Comprising more than 4.700 chemicals, per- and polyfluorinated alkyl substances (PFAS) are a group of anthropogenic chemicals, widely used to provide water and oil-repellency, that accumulate over time in humans and in the environment. Also known as “forever chemicals”, they are extraordinarily persistent in the environment and in our bodies, being toxic at extremely low levels (i.e., parts per quadrillion), posing significant risks to our health.

The EU’s Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability puts per- and polyfluorinated alkyl substances (PFAS) policy in the spotlight. Nowadays, a number of PFAS are on the REACH Candidate List of substances of very high concern (SVHC), while several additional PFAS are under evaluation. At the same time, the European Commission is committed to phasing out all PFAS, allowing their use only where they are proven to be irreplaceable and essential to society.

Regarding their use in surface treatments and coatings, PFAS are widely used to provide water and oil-repellency for various applications, such as non-sticking utensil pan surfaces, water repellent and anti-soiling treatment for textiles, food-contact anti-soiling coating on paper or cardboard packaging, and glass packaging. Alternative PFAS-free products are currently available on the market, but do not answer all market requirements in terms of long-term repellency properties (usually hydrophobic but not oleophobic), limiting their widespread use.

The BIO-SUSHY project represents a proactive step toward aligning innovative coating technologies with the EU's sustainability and safety goals.

The BIO-SUSHY project aims at developing innovative coating solutions based on two technologies, thermoplastic powder formulation and hybrid coatings based on the combination of glass-like sol-gel and organic (partially bio-based) chemistry, that will be designed to meet the policy ambition of the EU’s chemical strategy for sustainability toward a toxic free environment, following the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) methodology to ensure safety and environmental performances.

In this regard, an operating SSbD framework for the strategic development of hazard-safe PFAS-free repellent bio-based hybrid coatings is being developed. As we have applied it, we have encountered difficulties or challenges in implementing the SSbD framework, which will enable us to provide our experience to the JRC and policymakers to help refine it.

The main challenge BIO-SUSHY is addressing is the lack of new toxicological data. For instance, by screening the coatings through innovative biomembrane sensors and toxicological tests, the project will ensure that the coatings developed are both safe for human health and sustainable for the environment. The classification used to obtain the score in the first step of the SSbD framework is based on the Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) classification. This means that materials that are not required to comply with the CLP do not provide this information. Therefore, sufficient data cannot be obtained to assess the associated risk in accordance with the SSbD framework, leading to an underestimation of the real risk.

The proposed scoring system represents another challenge. The proposed scoring system is not suitable for all compounds, as in step four of the SSbD framework, where scoring is based on the improvement of new materials relative to the chosen benchmark. For example, in the case of biopolymer use, there is insufficient data to model it reliably, leading to excessive uncertainty. The scoring system, therefore, needs to be revised in this case. According to the current framework, in the absence of data, the proposed scoring system tends to indicate that compounds with limited data are safe, leading to an underestimation of the real risk.

The use of computational tools for mixtures is still insufficient, and for polymers is not adequate, because polymers are outside of the applicability domain for the Quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) models. Nanoparticles present the same challenge.

Presentation

<https://zenodo.org/records/17648989>

Recording

YouTube: <https://youtu.be/pEcDa8qIurU>

BIO-SUSHY

Link to website: <https://www.bio-sushy.eu/>

Email: info@bio-sushy.eu

About the Speaker

Pau Camilleri works as Project Manager of the Processes and Products Safety Unit at ITENE. Pau participates in international and national projects related to the implementation of the SSbD Framework, where it performs safety assessments of new products, analysing the entire process from early stages to the final product. She has studied Biotechnology, and holds three master's degrees: Food Biotechnology, Bioinformatics, and Packaging, Technology, Logistics and Transport. She has participated in the 2nd Safe and Sustainable by Design Bootcamp organised by PARC. ITENE develops biodegradable materials, additives, and novel bioplastics formulations with tailored functionalities focusing on improving main mechanical, barrier, and thermal properties to meet the demands of different/several packaging applications. These materials, often biobased and/or biodegradable, are designed to ensure product protection, maintaining or increasing their shelf-life while assuring their optimal end of life (industrial and home compostable, marine biodegradable, among others). The centre works on the formulation of new polymers, the incorporation of functional additives, and the optimisation of processing parameters to formulate high-tech blends. Several developments have led to patents, particularly in bioplastics derived from renewable sources and in the recovery of waste materials. This activity supports compliance with EU legislation and market expectations by enabling companies to reduce their environmental impact without compromising functionality or efficiency. ITENE has participated in and led EU-funded projects in this topic for over 20 years, pioneering projects such as SUSTAINPACK and, more recently, BIONANOPOLYS, SEALIVE, INSOIL, and Be-UP.

Talk 3

SSbD and the digital product passport

Centre for Research and Technology Hellas:

Dr Dimitrios-Sotirios Kourkoumpas

To turn the European ambitions into practice, the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC) is developing a harmonised Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework for chemicals and materials [1]. Within this broader context, the deployment of the SSbD framework is of strategic importance in the coatings sector, given its extensive chemical use, significant environmental releases, and high innovation potential.

In BIO4COAT, the Safe and Sustainable by Design framework ensures that each bio-coating formulation delivers its intended functionality while remaining within safety, environmental, and socio-economic boundaries throughout the entire life cycle. The hierarchical, five-stage methodology begins with a hazard assessment that evaluates the intrinsic hazard properties of the bio-based coating to identify potential welfare, environmental, or physical concerns early in development. The results are then interpreted in accordance with the Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) Regulation [2], resulting in an overall hazard score that determines whether the assessment can proceed to the next stage. The second stage involves an Occupational Health and Safety (OHS) assessment, which addresses potential exposure-related risks to human health and the environment during upstream processing, manufacturing, and end-of-life (EoL) stages, leveraging predictive exposure models and existing data sources to generate an aggregated OHS score. The third stage evaluates application-specific risks across representative bio-coating scenarios, generating scores for consumer and ecological safety. The fourth stage assesses environmental sustainability through a comprehensive Life Cycle Assessment (e-LCA) that covers the entire "cradle-to-grave" chain and aligns with ISO 14040/14044 Standards [3,4] to quantify impacts on air, soil, and water while identifying key environmental hotspots for targeted optimization or substitution. Finally, Life Cycle Costing (LCC) quantifies direct and indirect costs, identifies economic hotspots, and evaluates overall economic viability based on simulation-generated data [5].

Upon completing all stages, the individual scores are aggregated into a single SSbD score, offering a holistic overview of the bio-coating's safety, environmental, and economic performance. This score directly informs iterative design and production decisions to optimize both safety and sustainability outcomes.

Building on the SSbD framework, the Digital Product Passport (DPP) acts as a key digital enabler for implementing safety and sustainability principles within the BIO4COAT value chain. According to the EU Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) [7] and the Digital Product Passport Initiative under the Circular Economy Action Plan, the DPP is defined as a digital record containing standardized, product-specific data on materials, safety, environmental performance, and end-of-life options. It aims to enhance traceability, transparency, and circularity across product life cycles [6].

Within BIO4COAT, the DPP is implemented as a centralized digital platform that connects data from feedstock supply, biorefinery processes, coating formulation, and SSbD assessments, including hazard, OHS, application risk, e-LCA, and LCC. This integrated architecture enables secure and interoperable data sharing among industrial partners, research teams, and regulatory bodies, ensuring that sustainability and safety evidence are continuously embedded in design and production workflows. By linking each coating prototype to its corresponding data through unique digital identifiers, the DPP ensures full traceability across production, use, and end-of-life stages, while supporting compliance with EU sustainability reporting and data accessibility requirements.

Beyond its technical function, the DPP also serves as a collaborative interface that connects the diverse stakeholders involved in BIO4COAT. For industrial partners, it serves as a practical tool for enabling data-driven innovation, regulatory compliance, and streamlined documentation processes. For policymakers and regulatory authorities, it provides transparent and verifiable access to standardised sustainability information, reinforcing evidence-based policymaking and monitoring. Meanwhile, researchers and technical partners integrate experimental, life-cycle, and performance data into a unified environment, facilitating continuous SSbD optimisation and methodological refinement. By aligning these diverse perspectives within a single interoperable platform, the DPP strengthens coherence between research, industry, and policy efforts toward a safe and sustainable coatings sector.

Link to website: <https://www.bio4coat.eu/>

About the Speaker

Dr Dimitrios-Sotirios Kourkoumpas is a Senior Collaborating Researcher at the Centre for Research and Technology Hellas - Chemical Process & Energy Resources Institute (CERTH/CPERI). Dr Kourkoumpas holds a Diploma in Mechanical Engineering and an MSc in Energy Production and Management from the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), where he also completed his PhD in Mechanical Engineering, with a focus on sustainability and the circular economy. Dr Kourkoumpas' expertise lies in the simulation and development of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC), and Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) models for integrated advanced energy systems. His research focuses on the sustainable management of energy resources across environmental, economic, and social dimensions, under a circular economy framework.

He specializes in advanced biomass exploitation technologies, particularly biogas and biomethane, as well as renewable energy systems (RES), energy storage solutions, waste management, CO₂ utilization, smart factory design, and ecosystem restoration. At CERTH/CPERI, Dr Kourkoumpas leads the sustainability assessment team, overseeing LCA/LCC modelling and coordinating circular economy activities. He has served as a Senior Research Engineer and Project Manager on numerous EU- and nationally funded research initiatives, as well as on industrial projects. He is also a reviewer for several scientific journals. His research work has been published in peer-reviewed journals and presented at international conferences and workshops.

The Centre for Research and Technology Hellas - Chemical Process & Energy Resources Institute (CERTH/CPERI) is based in Greece. It is a research and technology organisation which conducts cutting-edge basic, applied, and technological research in areas such as clean energy, artificial intelligence, smart cities, precision medicine, and circular economy. CERTH/CPERI also transforms scientific knowledge into innovative applications, supporting industry collaboration, spin-offs, and sustainable economic growth. The teams develop state-of-the-art research infrastructure and participate in large-scale European and national projects to address societal and environmental challenges.

Talk 4

Fluorine-free coatings for textile, kitchenware and packaging applications

IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute: Dr Rosella Telaretti Leggieri

Growing concerns about the effects of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) on human health and the environment, along with increasing regulatory restrictions, have driven an urgent need for safer alternatives in coating applications where PFAS compounds are widely used.

The TORNADO project investigates novel fluorine-free coatings offering improved safety and sustainability compared to conventional water- and oil-repellent coatings. Three sectors that are relevant for coating applications are targeted: the textile, kitchenware, and packaging sectors. To ensure that the coatings developed within TORNADO comply with safety and sustainability requirements, TORNADO implements the European Union's Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework, integrating an SSbD assessment along the innovation process.

The project addresses the safety evaluation in accordance with the SSbD framework. Hazard and degradation profiles are compiled and continuously updated for all substances involved in the production of TORNADO coatings using a combination of scientific literature and in silico predictions based on Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationship (QSAR) models. In addition, a human health and environmental risk assessment of the manufacturing and processing steps as well as of the use phase of TORNADO coatings is performed. This assessment utilises exposure and environmental fate models available in the European Chemicals Agency's Chemical Safety Assessment and Reporting tool (CHESAR), specifically ECETOC Targeted Risk Assessment (TRA) and the European Union System for the Evaluation of Substances (EUSES). Several chemicals used in the investigated processes are new or uncommon, making data collection for risk assessment challenging. Therefore, a dedicated workflow was established to gather input data from both literature sources and in silico predictions. At the same time, project partners conduct environmental and social life cycle assessment. A comprehensive SSbD assessment aligned with the framework will be delivered through collaborative efforts in 2026.

Presentation

<https://zenodo.org/records/17648989>

Recording

YouTube: <https://youtu.be/CVzHcL7xfB0>

Project web page: <https://tornado-project.eu/>

About the Speaker

Rosella Telaretti Leggieri is a chemist with expertise in chemical and material related innovations, life cycle assessment, and risk assessment. She holds a PhD in fibre and polymer science and currently works at IVL as a researcher. The IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute is an independent non-profit organisation that combines applied research with consultancy services in the fields of the environment and sustainability (climate and energy, sustainable production, water, air quality, circular economy, among other areas).

Conclusions

Conclusions

Summary by Chiara Bearzotti and Estela López-Hermoso, based on the inputs from the authors of the four talks and the suggestions of the participants.

Future Work Perspectives for Researchers and Academia

- There is a need to continue building a robust, transferable methodological foundation that integrates SSbD, LCA, and DPP approaches for assessing complex chemical systems. This foundation will then provide practical guidance for redesigning and optimising coatings to improve SSbD compliance and overall sustainability performance.
- Comparative benchmarking between biobased and conventional coatings is needed to advance methodological refinement and data consistency, in support of businesses.
- The development of modular, interoperable digital infrastructures must link the safety, environmental, and socio-economic dimensions.
- Further empirical evidence must be collected to support the continuous improvement of the SSbD framework and strengthen its applicability across industrial sectors.

Future Work Perspectives for Industry and Manufacturers

- The scalability and cost-efficiency insights offered by the private sector can support smoother industrial upscaling and market deployment.
- A proactive SSbD implementation from the design stage will reduce long-term regulatory and operational risks. The DPP integration can also enable digital traceability, circular value chains, and smarter resource management.

Conclusions

Summary consolidated by Chiara Bearzotti and Estela López-Hermoso, based on the inputs provided by the authors of the four talks and on the suggestions of the participants.

Key Messages for Policymakers

Research can provide an evidence-based overview of the sustainability performance of biobased coatings throughout their life cycles. This evidence can inform future regulation and policy design.

- **Data gaps hinder SSbD implementation** - Materials not covered by CLP classification lack toxicological data, leading to underestimation of real risks and hampering proper safety assessment within the SSbD framework.
- **Computational tools need expansion** - Current QSAR models are inadequate for polymers, mixtures, and nanoparticles, limiting the ability to predict safety profiles for innovative biobased materials without extensive testing.
- **Early SSbD adoption reduces compliance risks** - Proactive integration of SSbD principles from the design stage helps industry avoid long-term regulatory challenges and supports smoother market deployment of sustainable innovations.
- **Digital Product Passports enable regulatory oversight** - DPP implementation provides policymakers with transparent, verifiable access to standardized sustainability and safety data across product lifecycles, supporting evidence-based regulation. The DPP implementation enables traceability, transparency, and data-driven oversight, fostering the implementation of the SSbD framework. It highlights the regulatory value of early SSbD adoption, helping prevent compliance gaps and accelerating the uptake of safe and sustainable innovations.
- **Cross-sector harmonization is essential** - The SSbD framework requires refinement for different material types and sectors, with scoring systems that accurately reflect safety-sustainability trade-offs rather than defaulting to "safe" classifications when data is absent.
- **Research-industry-policy alignment accelerates transition** - Clustering initiatives and collaborative platforms strengthen coherence between research outputs, industrial scalability considerations, and policy requirements, creating a unified pathway toward safer, circular coatings.

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- [8] Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials – Methodological guidance, Publications Office of the European Union, 2024, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/28450>
- [9] The P-A-R-C SSbD Toolbox <https://www.parc-ssbd.eu/> is a structured collection of tools to support designers, developers, and risk assessors of chemicals and materials from industry, academia, and government in addressing questions about functionality, chemical safety, and environmental sustainability. In addition, the toolbox will, in time, cover socio-economic aspects to support the exploratory work on a potential 5th step of the framework.
- [10] The project Mistra SafeChem is a research programme for green and sustainable chemical industry. The vision of Mistra SafeChem is to enable and promote the expansion of a safe, sustainable and green chemical industry. <https://mistrasafechem.se/>

Contributing Projects

Contributing Projects

The projects BIO4COAT, IRISS, TORNADO, BIO-SUSHY are funded by the European Commission under the European Union Research and Innovation Programme Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe and their European Partnerships, the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI JU) and the Circular Bio-Based Europe Joint Undertaking (CBE JU).

BIO4COAT: Biobased building blocks from biorefinery for safe diamond-like and biopolyurethane coating solutions under extreme and demanding conditions of use and end of life <https://www.bio4coat.eu>

IRISS: The International ecosystem for accelerating the transition to Safe-and-Sustainable-by-design materials, products and processes <https://iriss-ssbd.eu>

TORNADO: New routes of safe and sustainable by design water and oil repellent biobased coatings <https://tornado-project.eu>

BIO-SUSHY: Sustainable surface protection by glass-like hybrid and biomaterials coatings www.bio-sushy.eu

BIO-SUSHY

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